

Health, Safety & Environment Management – A Case Study of MCF Ltd., Mangalore

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ABSTRACT

Social justice and economic growth cannot be achieved without safe, **clean environment** as well as **healthy working conditions**. Safety and healthy working environment is regarded as a fundamental right of human being. The use of chemicals, the indiscriminate use of agro-chemicals like pesticides, agricultural machineries and equipment, industries with major accident risks, in many modern jobs pose serious safety, health and environmental risks. The fundamental purpose of National policy on **Health, safety and environment** at work place, is to eliminate the incidence of work related injuries, disease and disaster. At the same time to ensure occupational safety, health and environment **performance** through proactive approaches. Today most of the organisations strive for sustainability internally by providing workplace conditions that are conducive to employee's health and safety. Now safety, health and environment management has become a discipline that studies and implements practical aspect of an environmental protection and safety at work place. So, organisation must do to

make sure that their activities do not cause harmfulness to anyone. Their intention is to be enhancing the well-being of the employees and society at large. Organisation should encourage those attitudes and methods which will lead to improve physical, mental health of employees as well as environment.

MCF is the largest manufactures of chemical fertilizers in the State of Karnataka, India. The factory is located at Panambur, North of Mangalore city. The aim of the present case study is to find the safety and health measures adopted by MCF in order to protect the health of employees and also to know environmental management strategies developed to ensure welfare of the society.

Keywords: Social justice, clean environment, Healthy working conditions, Health, Safety and Environmental management & Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Social justice and economic growth cannot be achieved without safe, clean environment as well as healthy working conditions. Safety and healthy working environment is recognized as a fundamental right of human being. The use of chemicals, the indiscriminate use of agro-chemicals like pesticides, agricultural machineries and equipment, industries with major accident risks, in many modern jobs pose serious safety, health and environmental risks.

These days' workplace safety and health measures play a very important role in wellbeing of both employers and employees. The fundamental purpose of National policy on Health safety and environment at work place is to eliminate the incidence of work related injuries, disease and disaster. At the same time to ensure occupational safety, health and environment performance through proactive approaches.

Today most of the organisations strive for sustainability internally by providing work place conditions that are conducive to employee's health and safety. Now Environment, Health and Safety has become a discipline that studies and implements practical aspect of a environmental protection and safety at work place. All the industries must have safety risks but the management should devote their time to think and strategize the things that are required in their company to make sure that their workers are safe enough for all the time. Their intention is to be enhancing the wellbeing of the employees and society at large. Organisation should enlarge those attitudes and methods which will lead to improve physical, mental, health of employees as well as environment.

Conceptual frame work

The concept of EHS management approach introduced by chemical industry in the year 1985 as a reaction to several catastrophic accidents like the Seveso disaster of July 1976 and the Bhopal disaster of December 1984. Since the 1990s, general approaches to EHS management that may fit any type of organisation have appeared in International standards.

Safety means it involves creating organised efforts and procedures for identifying work place hazards and protection from accidents and exposure to harmful situations and substances. It also includes training of personnel in accident prevention, accident response, use of protective clothing and environment and emergency preparedness. Safety is one of the biggest issues and it is the responsibility of managers and business owners to make sure that their employees are working in safe environment or not.

Occupational safety and health is a multidisciplinary field concerned with the safety, health and welfare of people at work. Better health at its heart, so it is the duty lies with the organisation to develop safe, high quality and environmentally friendly process, working practices and systemic activities.

Environmental management system is a powerful tool for managing the adverse impacts of activities of an organisation on the environment aspects. An environmental management system can be developed in compliance with the ISO 14001 standard as part of an organisation's strategy to implement its environmental policy. Environmental management is the aspect of the organizations overall structure that addresses immediate and long term impacts of its products, services and processes on the environment. Environmental management system assists with planning, controlling and monitoring policies in an organisation. This study is undertaken to know health, safety and environmental management measures adopted by MCF Ltd.

About the company

Mangalore Chemicals and Fertilizers Limited, with a turnover of 3073.64 crores is the largest manufacturer of chemical fertilizers in the State of Karnataka, India. The factory is located at Panambur, 9 km North Mangalore city, on the banks of the Gurpur River, along the National Highway 66; opposite to the New Mangalore Port Trust. MCF is an ISO 14001 and OHS AS 18001 certified company. MCF is an Adventz Group; subsidiary of Zuari fertilizers and chemicals limited, single largest shareholder with 53.03 % shareholding. The company's corporate and registered office is at UB city, Bangalore and its factory unit is in Mangalore.

The main products are:

1. Urea
2. Di-Ammonium phosphate [DAP]
3. NP 20:20:00:13
4. Ammonium Bi-Carbonate [ABC]- Food grade, Sulphuric Acid, Speciality fertilizers and Nutrient products consisting of water soluble fertilizers, Micronutrients and soil conditioners and SulphonatedNaphthalene Formaldehyde (SNF).

The marketing offices of MCF are located in Karnataka, Kerala, Tamilnadu, Andra Pradesh, Telangana and Maharashtra.

Literature review

K. Logasakthi and k. Rajagopal (2013), in their article, “A Study on Employee Health, Safety and Welfare Measures of Chemical Industry in the View of Salem Region” examined the welfare measures taken in the chemical industry to protect the well-being of the employees. The study also examined about the employee’s satisfaction level, and identifying overall quality of work life of the employees.

Ms.P.Vinotha, Ms.R.Suriya and Ms.S.Valarmathi (2015), in their article,”A Study on Industrial Health and Safety Measures in H&R Johnson India Pvt. Ltd at Thennangudi” examined the health and safety measures which imply to improve the performance of the employees. Apart from that study also examined about to what extent safety equipments are necessary and in what ways it protect the employees from the accident. The study concludes with suggesting some measures useful for the company for their future development.

Dr.K. Nithyavathi(2016), ‘ ‘ A Study on Safety And Welfare Measures Provided to the Employees in Textile Industry in Tirupur District, examined the level of satisfaction of employees regarding safety and welfare measures. Apart from that study also examined about the perception of employees regarding safety and welfare measures provided to them. The study concludes with suggesting provision of more safety and welfare measures to improve the performance level of employees.

Ms. LincyJoykutty (2017), in his article,” A Study on Effectiveness of Safety and Health Programme on Workforce of Various Manufacturing Sectors, Bangalore” examined strategic issues pertaining to employee’s safety and health in various manufacturing organizations. Apart from that study examined about measures taken towards industrial safety through

standardised safety programmes. Accordingly the, study concludes with suggesting measures to reduce the occupational hazards in a manufacturing concerns.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the measures adopted by the company to develop healthy working conditions.
2. To identify the safety procedures of company to enhance the wellbeing of the workers.
3. To study the various programmes implemented by the company to improve its environmental performance.

Research methodology

The validity of any research lies to a great extent in the methodology followed. The methodology can be defined as, "A systematic and scientific description of how a particular study has been carried out". This study is coordinated by using the Secondary data. The use of annual reports of the company, journals, websites, are made in order to complete the study. The internal published documents of the company and other sources of materials provided substantial inputs for completing this study.

Limitations of the study

Every study has its limitations due to the unpredictable environment.

1. This study has been conducted for a shorter duration of time due to constraints.
2. As the top management personnel were busy and time conscious, it was not possible to meet them personally and to have discussion with them.

Discussions of the study

Safety measures followed by MCF Ltd

- A study reveals that MCF organizes various public awareness programmes to benefit the society.
- The study exhibits that the company adopt various measures in order to strengthen safety systems inside the factory like Emergency water spray system for Ammonia compressor house and Ammonia transfer pumps at Import Ammonia terminal was revamped and commissioned. Even company adopted fire alarm system consisting of beam type smoke detectors was installed in liquid fertilizer plant and multipurpose warehouse. A new breathing air compressor for filling breathing apparatus cylinders and fully encapsulated chemical protective suits were produced.

- As per the study it is observed that the company organises various training programmes to enhance the safety level of the employees. Training programmes relating to rescue operations, usage of personal protective environment, emergency management, work permit system, fire safety at home, safety, health and environment system etc.
- As per the study it is found that the regular mock drills were also conducted by the company to check the emergency preparedness and also firefighting training is conducted every Friday to train the employees and also contractor's workman.
- The study also reveals that company implemented Lock-out/Tag-out (LOTO) system throughout the plant to avoid accidents due to inadvertent release of hazardous energy and thereby enhancing safety of working personnel.
- The study exhibits that company organises Awareness campaigns like National safety day, fire service week and chemical disaster prevention in week undertaken to enhance the safety knowledge of employees.

Occupational health systems of MCF Ltd

- ❖ The study exhibits that the company makes arrangements for the medical examination of all the employees and contract workers which includes general physical examination, systemic examination and laboratory investigations.
- ❖ The study reveals that company adopts special tests to take care of health of the employees. Like pulmonary function test for employees who are exposed to dust and chemicals, audiometry for those exposed to noise and vision test for those who require high visual acuity. Study also observed that employees working in Ammonium Bicarbonate (ABC) plant were examined for communicable /skin diseases and were immunized against diseases like Hepatitis B and Typhoid.
- ❖ As per the study it is found that company organises various Health awareness programme in order to benefit their employees like Health and personal hygiene programme for the employees of the ABC plant and canteen workers, practical session on yoga for healthy living was conducted. Company even organises health awareness programmes on various subjects like Heart diseases, Alzheimer and Dementia and cancer, plastic surgery, Ergonomics –helping to work better, liver disorders causes and management, stress management, acidity diet and wellness diet for diabetics, Hazards

of dry abuse and prevention and swine-flu, kidney transplantation, stress management and work life balance etc. Conducted by expert to the employees.

- ❖ The study reveals that company also makes arrangements for organising health camps like Eye camps, Dental check-up and Blood donation camp in order to benefit the neighboring villages and schools.
- ❖ As per the study it is found that the company having its own medical team and they are engaged in delivering a talk on 'Occupational health and Hygiene 'for the employees of neighboring industries like MRPL, BASF,Adaniwilmen, OMPL etc.
- ❖ As per the study it is observed that the company not only makes medical examinationsbut at the same time employees with abnormal findings werecounseled and advised regarding further management.

Environmental management approaches of MCF

As an ISO 14001 certified company; many environmental management programmes have been implemented to improve the environmental performance of the company:

- The company has installed waste water treatment plant to treat, recycle and reuse the entire quantity of sewage and process effluents; there by company achieved a status of Zero liquid effluent discharge. This status is achieved by the company by making installation of Lamella clarifier, ultra filtration and reverse osmosis technologies for the treatment of trade effluent and Membrant Bio-reactor technology [MBR] for the treatment of domestic effluent.
- Rain water harvesting system and sewage treatment plants are installed at the township for employees.
- The company has planted about 63000 trees like Teak, mangium, Eucalyptus, Subabal, Acacia etc.The area covered by the green belt is about 64 acres. About 2000 additional saplings were planted during the year.
- Company installed continuous Ambinent Air quality monitoring station inside factory for continuous monitoring of ambient air quality.
- Ambinent Air quality data from CAAQM station is being displayed in LED display board at the entrance of the factory for public information.

- Company has also installed continuous online monitoring systems in Urea prill tower, Di Ammonium Phosphate plant stack and Sulphuric Acid plant stack as per Central Pollution Control Board guidelines.
- Separate environmental laboratory with all facility to carry out various analyses of environmental samples was setup.
- ‘E- waste collection facility’ has been provided inside the factory and also at MCF Township.
- LED lighting assembly is installed in various places inside the factory premises for conservation of energy.
- Environmental management system in line with ISO14001:2015 is implemented.
- ‘5-S’ system, a Japanese tool to improve housekeeping, up keep of plants and offices is implemented.
- Installed 1500 L capacity ‘ solar water heater ‘ with 16 collectors for industrial canteen and four solar street lights at factory premises and four solar lights at township.

Conclusion

MCF is a major fertilizer manufacturing industry in South India. It plays a vital role in increasing the agricultural output of farmers. This study was carried out as per the schedule and it was found that the organisation has provided sufficient health and safety measures to enhance the productivity level of employees. And even they adopt several measures to improve the environmental performance of the company. There is no doubt at all the company organizes various safety and health programmes to benefit the employees. But while observing the study workers or their representatives not allowed participating in safety and healthy decisionprogramme. So, it is better to encourage workers or their representatives to participate insafety andhealth programme decisions, it signals that management values their input into safety and health decisions.

References

Journals

1. Dr.K. Nithyavathi (2016), ‘ A Study on Safety and Welfare Measures provided to the Employees in Textile Industry in Tirupur District’, International Journal of Research in Management, Economics and Commerce, Vol.06, Iss: 10, pp.51-59.

2. K. Logasakthi and K.Rajagopal (2013),”A Study on Employee Health, Safety and Welfare Measures of Chemical Industry in the view of Salem Region, ‘Internal Journal of Research in Business Management, Vol.1, Iss: 1, pp.1-10.
3. LincyJoykutty (2017) ,” A Study on Effectiveness of Safety and Health Programmes on Work force of Various Manufacturing Sectors,Bangalore”,Global Journal of Management and Business Studies,Vol.7,Iss: 1,pp.1-13.
4. P.Vinutha, Ms.R. Suriya and Ms.S.Valarmathi (2015), ‘ A Study on Industrial Health and Safety Measures in H&R Johnson India Pvt. Ltd at Thennangudi’’, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Vol.5, Iss: 4.

Websites

5. [https:// www.mangalore chemicals.com](https://www.mangalorechemicals.com)
6. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/environment,-health-and-safety>
7. <https://vikaspedia.in/social-welfare/sector-safety-health-ad-environment-at-work-place>
